

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NDULUE****FIRST NAME: GOGO****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied U.S. U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

The plagiarism rate is: xx% (must be <18%)

Key concepts:

1. What is an academic essay? (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 1)
2. Elements of an academic essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 1)
3. Structure of an academic essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 3)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 5)
5. Citations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 6)
6. Writing Styles (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 24)
7. Style guides (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 24–26)

ACA-401D PERIOD 1 COURSEPACK

In this response paper, I will analyse ACA-401D Course pack for Period 1 and share my understanding of international academic writing Course after the first period.

1) INTRODUCTION

ACA-401D is the course code for International Academic Writing (Doctorate) course taught by Euclid University. It reviews the fundamentals of international academic writing, using proper English and rules of style (Euclid University n.d.).

This paper contains an explanation of the basics of essay writing, plagiarism and the proper use of citations, the importance of writing styles, and the application of style guides.

2) THE BASICS OF ESSAY WRITING: ELEMENTS AND STRUCTURES

An **academic essay** is a structured form of writing used to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence. An academic essay should answer a question or task (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 1).

a) Elements of an Academic Essay

There are various types of academic essays depending on the writers' purpose for writing and their writing style. However, all academic essays must possess a central idea or thesis, supporting facts, evidence (with appropriate references), and the analysis which is followed by a critical conclusion. These are the elements that make up an academic essay.

These elements must also be recognisable in each paragraph of the essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 2).

b) Structure of an Academic Essay

Academic essays generally begin with clear introductions that provide the focus and direction of the essay, followed by the body of the essay containing paragraphs that offer exposition and evidence to develop your argument. The essay always ends with a conclusion that re-summarises the main points including possible implications, future directions for research based on the evidence presented.

Despite the established need for structure in essay writing, I agree with the argument made in the ACA-401D Coursepack for Period 1 that essay writing is not necessarily a linear process.

3) PLAGIARISM AND THE PROPER USE OF CITATIONS

a) Plagiarism

Plagiarism is the use of someone else's ideas, words, statistics/data, or visuals without giving credit to the author. Plagiarism is always unfair to the author, unethical and it constitutes a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences. Cleenewerck and Gulma point out:

When writing papers, one of the most important things the writer should do is avoid Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 5).

b) Citations

Plagiarism in academic essay writing is avoided with the use of proper citations. Citations are a writing tool used to indicate to the reader where a piece of information came from (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 6).

There are two ways citations can be applied. These are:

i) *In-text citations*

These are applied when the body of work from which you have sourced your information is recognised within the actual text itself. For example: “Using signal phrases introduces a quotation or paraphrase by using a verb and mentioning the author’s name” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 10).

In-text citations are commonly used to cite quotations or paraphrases and are usually applied in short articles or essays.

ii) *List of works cited*

This method of citation recognises the sources of information cited in the academic paper at the end of the body of work. It is the ‘references’ or ‘bibliography’.

4) WRITING STYLES AND APPLICATION OF STYLE GUIDES

In literature, **writing style** is the manner of expressing thought in language characteristic of an individual, period, school, or nation (“Writing Style” 2021).

The style guide recommended by Euclid university is the Chicago Rules (Turabian) for in-text reference and ‘Works Cited/Reference List’ entries (Euclid University n.d.).

Style guides are necessary to ensure consistency and coherence in cases where multiple authors are involved in a single body publication. Style guides are also particularly relevant in technical writing to eliminate ambiguity.

In addition to the usage of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary, Cleenewerck and Gulma propose:

Writing Style encompasses many different aspects like preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font usage, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling (UK v US for example), readership considerations, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, the use of symbols, voice preferences (active v passive), structure, paragraph numbering and indentation, the use of headings, the use of lists, trademark or branding considerations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 24–26).

5) CONCLUSION

After studying the ACA-401D Period 1 Coursepack, I am confident of my understanding of what academic essays are and how to write good essays (from planning to essay submission).

The knowledge gained from the ACA-401D Period 1 Coursepack are invaluable in subsequent response papers and for International Academic Writing.

REFERENCES

Cleenerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 3rd ed. Bangui: Euclid University.

Euclid University. n.d. "ACA-401D Period 1 – EUCLID University LMS." EUCLID University LMS. Accessed November 8, 2021. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

"Writing Style." 2021. In Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Writing_style&oldid=1053646605.

Cleenerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.